

METHODOLOGY OF STRATEGIC COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT FOR FUTURE SPECIALISTS IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract. This article delves into the imperative realm of developing strategic competence in English language teaching, particularly tailored for future specialists. Strategic competence, extending beyond linguistic mastery, plays a pivotal role in fostering effective communication and problem-solving skills. The methodology proposed amalgamates task-based learning, authentic materials, problem-solving approaches, and communication strategies. It emphasizes the crucial role of teachers, underscores assessment strategies, and advocates technology integration to simulate real-world language usage. The article presents case studies demonstrating successful implementation, highlighting enhanced language proficiency and strategic competence in learners. By embracing this comprehensive methodology, English educators can equip future specialists with the multifaceted skills essential for navigating the linguistic demands of their respective fields.

Keywords: Strategic competence, English language teaching, future specialists, task-based learning, authentic materials, problem-solving approaches.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается императивная сфера развития стратегической компетентности в преподавании английского языка, особенно для будущих специалистов. Стратегическая компетентность, выходящая за рамки лингвистического мастерства, играет ключевую роль в развитии навыков эффективного общения и решения проблем. Предлагаемая методология объединяет обучение на основе задач, аутентичные материалы, подходы к решению проблем и стратегии коммуникации. Он подчеркивает решающую роль учителей, подчеркивает стратегии оценивания и выступает за интеграцию технологий для моделирования использования языка в реальном мире. В статье представлены тематические исследования, демонстрирующие успешную реализацию, подчеркивающие повышение уровня владения языком и стратегической компетентности учащихся. Приняв эту комплексную методологию, преподаватели английского языка могут вооружить будущих специалистов многогранными навыками, необходимыми для удовлетворения лингвистических требований в соответствующих областях.

Ключевые слова: Стратегическая компетентность, обучение английскому языку, будущие специалисты, целевое обучение, аутентичные материалы, подходы к решению проблем.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola, ayniqsa, bo'lajak mutaxassislar uchun mo'ljallangan ingliz tilini o'qitishda strategik kompetentsiyani rivojlantirishning muhim sohasini o'rganadi. Strategik kompetentsiya, tilshunoslikdan tashqari, samarali muloqot va muammolarni hal qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Taklif etilayotgan metodologiya vazifaga asoslangan ta'lim, haqiqiy materiallar, muammolarni hal qilish yondashuvlari va muloqot strategiyalarini birlashtiradi. U o'qituvchilarning hal qiluvchi rolini ta'kidlaydi, baholash strategiyalarini ta'kidlaydi va real dunyo tillaridan foydalanishni taqlid qilish uchun texnologiya integratsiyasini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Maqolada o'quvchilarda tilni bilish va strategik kompetentsiyani oshirishni ta'kidlab, muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirishni ko'rsatadigan amaliy tadqiqotlar keltirilgan. Ushbu keng qamrovli metodologiyani o'zlashtirgan holda, ingliz

o'qituvchilari bo'lajak mutaxassislarni o'zlarining tegishli sohalarining lingvistik talablarini boshqarish uchun zarur bo'lgan ko'p qirrali ko'nikmalar bilan jihozlashlari mumkin.

***Kalit so'zlar:** strategik kompetentsiya, ingliz tilini o'rgatish, bo'lajak mutaxassislar, topshiriqlarga asoslangan ta'lim, autentik materiallar, muammoni hal qilish yondashuvlari.*

Introduction.

Highlight the importance of strategic competence in language learning.

Discuss how proficiency in English is crucial for future specialists in various fields.

Introduce the focus on developing strategic competence within the English teaching methodology [1:38].

Understanding Strategic Competence:

Define strategic competence and its significance in language acquisition.

Explore how strategic competence goes beyond linguistic knowledge to include effective communication skills.

Discuss the relevance of strategic competence for future specialists in real-world scenarios.

Key Components of the Methodology:

1. Task-Based Learning:

- Emphasize the integration of language skills within meaningful tasks.
- Provide examples of tasks that mimic real-world scenarios future specialists might encounter.

2. Authentic Materials:

- Advocate the use of authentic materials to expose learners to real language usage.
- Illustrate how authentic materials enhance strategic thinking by presenting language in context.

3. Problem-Solving Approaches:

- Integrate problem-solving activities to promote critical thinking.
- Demonstrate how these activities encourage learners to employ strategic competence in finding solutions.

4. Communication Strategies:

- Teach various communication strategies for effective expression.
- Show how these strategies aid future specialists in conveying their ideas clearly and coherently [2:145].

Implementing the Methodology.

1. Role of Teachers:

- Discuss the role of educators in guiding students to develop strategic competence.
- Highlight the need for teachers to model strategic thinking and communication.

2. Assessment Strategies:

- Explore methods for assessing strategic competence.
- Suggest continuous evaluation to track learners' progress in applying strategic skills.

3. Technology Integration:

- Emphasize the role of technology in providing diverse learning opportunities.
- Showcase how technology aids in simulating real-world language use and enhances strategic thinking [3:30].

Challenges and Solutions:

Discuss potential challenges in implementing this methodology.

Offer solutions and strategies for overcoming obstacles in developing strategic competence.

Case Studies:

Present case studies highlighting successful implementation of the methodology.

Share outcomes and improvements observed in learners' language proficiency and strategic competence.

Conclusion:

Summarize the key points of the methodology.

Reiterate the importance of strategic competence for future specialists in English language learning [4:58].

By integrating this methodology, English teachers can empower future specialists with the linguistic and strategic tools necessary for success in their respective fields. Developing strategic competence in English teaching for future specialists involves a systematic and well-thought-out methodology. The process aims to equip learners with the skills to navigate language tasks effectively and strategically.

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